

“ORAL SPEECH IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES DEVELOPMENT”

Sattarova Durdona

Termez State Pedagogical Institute in Foreign Languages and Literature Faculty

Abstract: Vocabulary work is the beginning of improving written speech is the point. The words in the dictionary are combined based on grammatical rules. performs a certain communicative function.

Key words: skill, technique, monologue, content of the text

The better the vocabulary is reduced, the more a person's oral and written speech so rich. Form written speech skills by copying various notes It is a means of making, mastering writing techniques and writing works It helps to be meaningful and to define the artistic style. Copy the inscriptions are mainly those at the bottom:

1. Copying landscape and portrait images in works of art.
2. Preparation of monologues from the speech of the participants of the play move for the purpose of.
3. Copy poems or excerpts from them for memorization, recitation.

Writing dialogues by turning them into diminutive sentences, in works of art copy the dialogues and write them by turning them into diminutive sentences, connected It helps a lot to understand the written speech. Such an exercise is creative thinking, literate and helps to make concise sentences.

Writing the content of poetic works with a plot, turning them into a story. In order to memorize the content of many poetic works with plots it is also important to convert their content into prose. This is a unique creative exercise in the field of written speech. For example, A. Navoi's The content of the poetic parable "Liar" can be written in prose. Writing answers to questions prepares the reader to write narratives and essays, to deepen the content of works of art, to be able to analyze them. helps to improve. Answer the questions with as many quotes as possible writing, depending on the requirement of the question, focus on the most important issues should be done.

It is known that the person who shortens the content of the text and thinks much more deeply than the person who writes it It requires a level of skill and experience to abbreviate large-scale artistic writing works are selected and attention is required to the following:

1. First of all, the work will be completely flowed.

2. The most important points are determined and a rough plan is drawn up.

3. Based on the plan, the content of the work is written in abbreviated form:

Expanding the content of the text is also one of the types of creative writing. With that in one line, expanding the content of folk proverbs or connecting it to a text writing is one of the best ways. Dictation is important in improving students' writing and speaking is important. Dictation is like copying spoken speech into written speech is a special type. Narrative is one of the main types of written work, and the reader's speech helps improve skills. Substitution of written speech when writing a statement at the same time, serious importance is given to the educational, educational and educational side of the text is given.

Essay is a unique creative work, written speech is one of the main means of development. All types of essays are for students with educational goals in mind plays an important role in conveying the speech. Written speech is distinguished from oral speech by the following features: speech while writing, the author has the opportunity to think freely in terms of time. It is little repeatedly editing parts of speech and whole speech. That's why written speech is more fluent than spoken speech. Any speech is the external appearance of the text addressed to the listener or reader by a certain arranger or writer. Of course it is

only if the hired speech reaches the listener and has a certain effect on him we can say a good speech. The speech is not enough to be good in every way sets certain requirements. These requirements are the main speech are called qualities, characteristics. They are correctness of speech, logicity, effectiveness, cleanliness, comprehensibility, and is appropriateness.

1. Correctness of speech. "Rightness," writes V.G. Kostomarov, - speech

Literary language is accepted at a certain time as a necessary and first condition of culture that it strictly and precisely complies with the established norm, its pronunciation, spelling dictionary and we need to understand the acquisition of fammatic norms.

Correctness of speech is its most important communicative quality.

If the speech is not correct, other communicative qualities will also be destroyed. If the structure of the speech is not correct, its logic, accuracy, purpose compatibility is also compromised. In order for speech to be correct, there are mainly two norms - accent and grammar requires strict adherence to the norm. With the shift of emphasis in the words It should not be forgotten that the meaning can sometimes change. This also causes speech disorders: Apples and apples; now and then, little by little; our reader-our reader, new-new, etc

The meaning of the logical (logical) accent that falls on one sound in the sentence the difference is great.

Observance of grammatical norms is one of the rules of sentence formation correct use, make mistakes when adding ingredients and additives not to put, to use the adverbs in the place of little, have and appropriateness of the section, second-order children are connected to them laws are understood.

2. Clarity of speech - to the reality expressed by the words is absolutely appropriate and compatible. Clarity of speech is important It has been known since ancient times as one of its qualities. Both Western thinkers and Eastern scientists talk about accuracy which are considered to be the first condition of their qualities. Aristotle: "If the speech is unclear, it will not achieve its goal," said Kaykovuz "O child, know the face and back of the word, follow them do it, speak fluently when tuning, this is a sign of eloquence. If what the meaning of the word is when you speak it if you don't know, you're like a bird..." he says.

REFERENCES:

1. Ismailova Gulmira. (2023). Rol proizvodnyx deystviy i rechi v razvitiy lichnosti rebenka. *Medicine, pedagogy and technology: theory and practice*, 1(2), 23–28. Izvlecheno ot <https://universalpublishings.com/~niverta1/index.php/mpttp/article/view/2320>
2. "Rules of spelling in words" 2020
3. "Grammatic norm" 2016
4. "A poetic work with a plot" 1997